

***sabinaNSDM*: an R package for spatially-nested hierarchical species distribution modeling**

Rubén G. Mateo^{1,2*}, Jennifer Morales-Barbero^{1*}, Alejandra Zarzo-Arias^{1,3}, Herlander Lima⁴, Teresa Goicolea¹

¹ Departamento de Biología, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

² Centro de Investigación en Biodiversidad y Cambio Global (CIBC-UAM), Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

³ Universidad de Oviedo, Asturias, Spain

³ Universidad de Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain

* Equal contribution

ABSTRACT

1. Species distribution models (SDMs) have evolved to combine species-environment interactions across multiple scales. Spatially-nested hierarchical models (NSDMs) offer a promising avenue by integrating datasets and predictive models from broad to fine scales. But a user-friendly tool to execute these models remains an important ongoing challenge.
2. To address this gap, we introduce the *sabinaNSDM* R package that provides a straightforward approach to develop NSDMs. This package merges global scale models, capturing extensive ecological niches, with regional scale models featuring high-resolution covariates, to form a unified hierarchical modeling framework. This toolkit is designed to facilitate the implementation of NSDMs for ecologists,

conservationists, and researchers aiming to produce more reliable species distribution predictions.

3. *sabinaNSDM* streamlines the data preparation, calibration, integration, and projection of models across two scales. It automates (if necessary) the generation of background points, spatial thinning of species occurrence data, covariate selection, and the generation of NSDMs.
4. This paper outlines the workflow and functions integrated into the *sabinaNSDM* package, complemented by an applied case study involving a pool of 76 tree species. Consistent with previous publications, the generated NSDMs facilitated precise predictions (mean AUC value through independent evaluation higher than 0.88) of species distributions under current and future environmental scenarios.

KEYWORDS

Ecological Niche Models, Ensemble Modeling, Hierarchical Modeling, Species Distribution Models, Scale, Spatial Ecology, Niche truncation

1 INTRODUCTION

The origin of species distribution models (SDMs, Guisan, Thuiller & Zimmermann 2017; Araújo *et al.* 2019) in the 1980s (see, Booth *et al.* 2014, and references therein) marked a central moment in ecology, stating a new era of understanding the relationship between species distributions and their environment (Guisan & Zimmermann 2000). SDMs have since become vital tools in conservation biology (Guisan *et al.* 2013), and biogeography (Araújo & Guisan 2006). Nowadays, they play a crucial role in understanding the potential impacts of global and climate change on the environment (Guisan, Thuiller & Zimmermann 2017). Over the decades, methodological advancements have enhanced the

reliability of these models (Araújo *et al.* 2019; Zurell *et al.* 2020; Sillero *et al.* 2021; Moudry *et al.* Under Review). However, despite their utility, SDMs face challenges like niche truncation and limited transferability across spatial and temporal scales (Thuiller *et al.* 2004; Petitpierre *et al.* 2016; Chevalier *et al.* 2022). These challenges primarily arise because the efficacy of SDMs depends on properly capturing the complete ecological niche of species (Gallien *et al.* 2012; Guisan, Thuiller & Zimmermann 2017). Yet, in practice, these models are frequently constrained to specific geographic extents, such as a country in national conservation assessments (Scherrer *et al.* 2021), which can lead to truncating the environmental range—and by extension, the species niche—considered during model training (Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Goicolea *et al.* In Press; Guisan *et al.* Under review). This methodological shortfall can lead to significant bias in spatial and temporal projections (see, Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Goicolea *et al.* In Press), highlighting a widespread issue within the SDM community that challenge the applicability of national or regional assessments (Chevalier *et al.* 2021; Scherrer *et al.* 2021). There is need for a user-friendly methodological framework to address this issue that enhance the applicability of SDMs in terms of applied management and conservation solutions.

Spatially-nested hierarchical species distribution models (NSDMs) emerged as a comprehensive solution (Mateo *et al.* 2019a; Guisan *et al.* Under review), that ensures the representation of the complete ecological (generally climatic) niche of species and the generation of fine-resolution predictions (Mateo *et al.* 2019a; Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Adde *et al.* 2023a). Different studies have shown that hierarchical models outperform their non-hierarchical counterparts in various applications, including conservation planning (Mateo *et al.* 2019b), restoration (Carrillo-García *et al.* 2023), and assessing the impacts of climate change (Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Goicolea *et al.* In Press). Furthermore, this

methodology accounts for environmental predictors (covariates) at their operating scales (Mateo, Mokany & Guisan 2017; Mateo *et al.* 2019a), allowing to acknowledge the complexity of ecological processes and the diverse factors influencing species distributions (McGill 2010). NSDMs integrate a global-scale SDM that captures the species' ecological tolerances to broad-scale drivers, such as macroclimate, with a regional-scale SDM that captures important regional drivers of species distributions, including landscape features and microtopography (Mateo, Mokany & Guisan 2017; Mateo *et al.* 2019a).

Over the recent decades, numerous statistical techniques for species distribution modeling have been introduced across various platforms and R packages (Sillero *et al.* 2023), each offering distinct outcomes (Elith *et al.* 2006; Mateo *et al.* 2010). Ensemble SDMs (Araújo & New 2007; Marmion *et al.* 2009) that combine multiple statistical techniques have shown to be an effective strategy to generate more reliable SDM predictions and avoid relying on unique strategies. The R package *biomod2* (Thuiller *et al.* 2009) is notable for its proven efficacy to deliver ensemble models through numerous applications and citations (GS 2364, 12/03/2024)

Various methods and approaches have been suggested for calibrating NSDMs (see, Guisan *et al.* Under review, for a review). A recent development in this domain is the N-SDM pipeline (Adde *et al.* 2023a), that pioneered a first end-to-end NSDM platform designed for Linux environments and high-performance computers. However, there is still no tool available to directly generate NSDMs across various operating systems. Here, we introduce a novel R package (*sabinaNSDM*) based on the spatially-nested hierarchical approach that facilitates the combination of SDMs at two different scales. This package

was built around the principle of ensemble modelling (Araújo & New 2007; Marmion *et al.* 2009) and the *biomod2* package (Thuiller *et al.* 2009) that combine multiple statistical approaches. Additionally, *sabinaNSDM* enhances modeling capabilities by offering support for different types of hierarchical models.

This new *sabinaNSDM* package provides users with a holistic toolset that integrates (a) the generation of background data (Acevedo *et al.* 2012; Mateo *et al.* 2015), (b) preparation and spatial thinning of species occurrences (based on the *ecospat* package, (Di Cola *et al.* 2017), (c) environmental covariate selection (based on the *covsel* package, (Adde *et al.* 2023b), and (d) NSDMs calibration, evaluation and projection. The package stands out for its ability to automate data preparation and model parameterization with commonly used options in current research (Guisan, Thuiller & Zimmermann 2017; Araújo *et al.* 2019), offering users an intuitive platform. The package emerges as a comprehensive solution that addresses both the need for complex hierarchical models and the simplicity required for efficiently executing them.

2 THE *sabinaNSDM* PACKAGE

Through its seven functions (Table 1), the *sabinaNSDM* package streamlines the process in three steps: (a) data preparation; (b) single scale (global and regional) modeling; and (c) the spatially-nested hierarchical combination of previous models using two approaches (“covariate” and “multiply”) and different parameters options.

The current release can be installed from the GitHub repository with the following code: `remotes::install_github("geoSABINA/sabinaNSDM")`. In the supporting information, detailed examples are provided on how to execute the package functions for both single

species (Supporting Information S1) and multiple species (Supporting Information S2) in parallel using the *furrr* package (Vaughan & Dancho 2022).

2.1.1 Data preparation

The package equips users with tools for importing and harmonizing datasets across two different spatial scales (see, Mateo *et al.* 2019a; Guisan *et al.* Under review): global data (i.e., wide spatial extents optimally covering the entire species' range and usually with coarse resolution) and regional data (spatially constrained but usually more precise). For this purpose, the user should upload species occurrence data and environmental covariates at both scales. The *NSDM.InputData()* function integrates the data at both scales and creates the input object necessary for the following steps. When the user has previous absence/pseudo-absence/background data, they can also be imported here.

Species occurrence data should be provided as a data frame with two columns (x and y coordinates). Global species occurrences might be obtained from global datasets such as Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; www.gbif.org) useful to obtain broad-scale information. Regional species occurrences can be obtained from more precise national or regional biodiversity databases (see, Mateo *et al.* 2019a; Guisan *et al.* Under review).

Environmental covariates for each scale must be provided as a *SpatRaster* object, with each band corresponding to a different covariate. Global covariates usually comprise only climate variables, while regional scale can include other thematic categories relevant for species distribution (e.g., topographic, edaphic, hydrologic, land use and cover, etc.) and usually only available at regional extents. New scenarios (e.g., future climatic

representative concentration pathways or climate models) can be provided to generate model projections. Species occurrences and environmental covariates at each spatial scale must have matching coordinate projection systems.

2.1.2 Background generation and spatial filtering

When absences/pseudo-absences/background data is not provided, the *NSDM.FormattingData()* function of the package generates 10,000 (by default, but user-customizable) random background points for each scale (Acevedo *et al.* 2012; Mateo *et al.* 2015). Alternatively, users can generate background points through a stratified process (Guisan, Thuiller & Zimmermann 2017; see chapter 7.4.3 for more details). The stratified method is based on a PCA analysis from all environmental covariates, where the two principal component values are divided into quartiles and multiplied to generate a total stratified variable of 16 categories (stratums). Then, the background points are generated randomly according to the area occupied by each stratum based on the *sgsR* R package (Goodbody *et al.* 2023).

Additionally, this function refines global and regional species occurrences by removing locations without covariate data, removing duplicates, and employing spatial thinning with the *ecospat* package (Di Cola *et al.* 2017) enforcing a minimum distance criterion user-defined or by default, based on the covariates' resolution at each scale.

2.1.3 Variable selection

The *NSDM.SelectCovariates()* function of the *sabinaNSDM* package selects the most suitable subset of environmental covariates at both global and regional scales for each species using the *covsel* package (Adde *et al.* 2023b). The user can choose to include or

exclude climate variables on the regional scale calibration. Even though climate data is excluded from the regional models, climate data should be always provided at the regional scale to facilitate the global model projection at regional scale and resolution. To accommodate diverse modeling needs, the package allows users to adjust the Pearson correlation filter threshold, with a default setting of 0.7, and specify the maximum number of variables to be included in the model at global and regional scale.

2.1.4 Single-scale models: global and regional

sabinaNSDM uses the *biomod2* package (Thuiller *et al.* 2009) to develop ensemble single-scale models at both global and regional scales. At the global scale, the *NSDM.Global()* function utilizes the available species occurrence data at the global scale and the preselected global-scale covariates. Global-scale models aim to encapsulate species' entire niche and are subsequently projected onto regional-scale covariates. The *NSDM.Regional()* function calibrates regional models using regional scale species occurrence data alongside preselected environmental covariates.

The two single-scale functions offer users the flexibility to personalize the modeling process to their needs. This includes selecting the statistical algorithms and parameters, setting the number of cross-validation replicates (the default is 10), and determining the data percentage for calibration in each replicate (the default is 80%). The resulting ensemble predictions average the outputs of single-algorithm models, discarding those with an AUC below 0.8 (by default, but user-customizable). Furthermore, the two single-scale functions create binary models based on ROC and TSS thresholds, compute a range of seven evaluative statistics (ROC, TSS, KAPPA, ACCURACY, SR, BOYCE, MPA;

see Thuiller et al 2009 for more details), and determine variable significance based on *biomod2* (Thuiller *et al.* 2009).

2.1.5 Spatially-nested hierarchical models: covariate and multiply

The principal feature of the *sabinaNSDM* package is its spatially-nested hierarchical modeling framework, which integrates global- and regional-scale models. Two main hierarchical model approaches can be generated: “covariate” and “multiply” (see, Adde *et al.* 2023a). Covariate models calibrate a regional-scale model incorporating the global model output as an additional covariate (Mateo *et al.* 2019a; Goicolea *et al.* In Press). Additionally, the package allows for a secondary variable cleansing process, to potentially remove covariates that are correlated with the global model. The same modeling parameters and saving options as the single-scale models of the previous step can be adjusted for covariate hierarchical models. Covariate hierarchical models can be generated with the *NSDM.Covariate()* function.

The hierarchical multiply model averages the outputs of global and regional models with different averaging options (arithmetic or geometric mean). It is possible to rescale the predictions of the global and the regional models to have the same minimum and maximum values (see, Mateo *et al.* 2019b). Multiply NSDM models can be generated with the *NSDM.Multiply()* function.

2.2 Applied example

We used 76 tree species in Spain to illustrate the functions and performance of the *sabinaNSDM* package. The global scale of our example covered completely the European biomes (Olson et al. 2001) and aimed to capture species’ ecological tolerance to broad-

scale macroclimate at 5 km resolution. The regional scale was peninsular Spain and was designed to capture local drivers influencing species distribution at 1 km resolution. Twenty percent of the regional species occurrences were kept aside for an independent evaluation.

We generated single-scale global and regional models, and NSDM with both covariate and multiply approaches for the 76 species under current and two simulated future scenarios. See Supporting Information S3 for methodological details (environmental covariates, species occurrence data, statistical algorithms, future scenarios, etc.). A covariates subset, a single future climatic scenario, and occurrence data for two species are provided for download as examples to test the functionality of the package.

We compared the performance of single-scale and NSDMs for the 76 species according to the evaluation species occurrence dataset and the AUC statistic (Table 2). Additionally, we compared the prediction patterns of the different models with the Pearson correlation coefficient (Table 3).

The single-scale and NSDMs for the 76 were successfully created. The NSDMs outperformed, or at least matched their single-scale counterparts (Table 2). As expected (Mateo *et al.* 2019a; Mateo *et al.* 2019b), NSDMs were more similar to regional models than global models (Table 3, Figure 2) for current and future climatic scenarios.

3 DISCUSSION

One of the key strengths of *sabinaNSDM* lies in its ability to address niche truncation and environmental extrapolation issues (Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Goicolea *et al.* In Press). By ensuring that models are informed by a comprehensive range of environmental

conditions, *sabinaNSDM* reduces the likelihood of prediction errors associated with models calibrated on truncated niches (Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Goicolea *et al.* In Press). This is particularly crucial for forecasting species' responses to climate change, where accurate representation of ecological niches is paramount (Guisan *et al.* Under review).

Unlike other packages available in R for ecological niche modeling, *sabinaNSDM* stands out for its spatially-nested hierarchical approach, allowing users to combine models at different spatial scales. One of the pivotal design goals of the *sabinaNSDM* package is to perform NSDMs while prioritizing simplicity and accessibility for users, making advanced hierarchical modeling techniques accessible across various computing environments and for a broader audience.

The superior performance of hierarchical models across multiple species produced by *sabinaNSDM* matches with results from previous studies (Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Adde *et al.* 2023a; Goicolea *et al.* In Press). NSDMs also have the advantage of generating more reliable predictions at other spatial or temporal scale (Mateo *et al.* 2019a; Mateo *et al.* 2019b; Chevalier *et al.* 2021; Chevalier *et al.* 2022; Adde *et al.* 2023a; Goicolea *et al.* In Press; Guisan *et al.* Under review). By providing accurate and scalable predictions of species potential distributions, *sabinaNSDM* enables more targeted conservation efforts, identification of priority areas for protection and resources allocation, and informed decision-making in the face of environmental change, among many other applications (Guisan *et al.* Under review). Therefore, the outputs produced by *sabinaNSDM* are valuable for conservation planning and management.

4 CONCLUSIONS

sabinaNSDM represents a significant advancement in species distribution modeling, offering an easy to implement tool for modeling species distributions under a spatially-nested hierarchical approach. *sabinaNSDM* is a holistic tool that facilitates (a) the creation of background data, (b) preparation and spatial thinning of species occurrences, (c) environmental covariate selection, and (d) the integration of global and regional scale models into NSDMs. NSDMs are useful modeling techniques to address niche truncation and to enhance the accuracy and ecological relevance of SDMs predictions. Therefore, *sabinaNSDM* provides a powerful tool for conservationists and ecologists. Future developments and applications of *sabinaNSDM* will continue to refine our understanding of species-environment relationships and support effective biodiversity conservation in an era of rapid environmental change.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Framework of nested spatial hierarchical species distribution models (red lines) using the two different approaches (“covariate” and “multiply”) applied in the *sabinaNSDM* package.

Figure 2. Comparative display of four modeling approaches (Global, Regional, Covariate, and Multiply) under current climatic conditions for *Juniperus sabina* L., one of the 76 species analyzed in this study.

TABLES

Table 1. The seven functions of the *sabinaNSDM* package and their main objectives.

Step	Package function	Objective
Data preparation	NSDM.InputData	Provides the package the species occurrence and environmental variables at both global and regional scales
	NSDM.FormattingData	Background data generation and species occurrence filtering
	NSDM.SelectCovariates	Selects uncorrelated and the most relevant environmental covariates
Single scale modeling	NSDM.Global	Calibrates, evaluates, and projects ensemble models at global scale
	NSDM.Regional	Calibrates, evaluates, and projects ensemble models at regional scale
Nested modeling	NSDM.Covariate	Generate spatially-nested hierarchical species distribution models with the covariate approach. The covariate approach uses the output of the global model as an additional covariate for the regional scale model
	NSDM.Multiply	Generate spatially-nested hierarchical species distribution models with the multiply approach. The multiply approach averages the global and regional models

Table 2. Mean AUC value and standard deviation (in brackets) for the independent evaluation of the two single scale (global and regional models) and the two spatially-nested hierarchical (covariate and multiply) generated for the 76 species.

Global	Regional	Covariate	Multiply
0.7941	0.8832	0.8852	0.8791
(0.1160)	(0.0714)	(0.0701)	(0.0739)

Table 3. Mean value and standard deviation (in brackets) of the Pearson correlation coefficient when comparing the two single scale (global and regional models) and the two spatially-nested hierarchical (covariate and multiply) generated for the 76 species under current and two future climatic scenarios.

	Global vs. Regional	Global vs. Covariate	Global vs. Multiply	Regional vs. Covariate	Regional vs. Multiply	Covariate vs. Multiply
Current	0.5966 (0.1805)	0.6337 (0.1740)	0.7554 (0.1379)	0.9623 (0.0559)	0.9599 (0.0297)	0.9427 (0.0641)
Scenario 1	0.6250 (0.2464)	0.6516 (0.2621)	0.8845 (0.1284)	0.9292 (0.0806)	0.8653 (0.1464)	0.8454 (0.1581)
Scenario 2	0.6253 (0.2497)	0.6512 (0.2722)	0.8897 (0.1172)	0.9214 (0.0816)	0.8502 (0.1560)	0.8297 (0.1661)

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Rubén G. Mateo conceived the package; all the authors designed, tested, and wrote the functions and documentation of the package. Rubén G. Mateo wrote the first version of the manuscript; all the authors contributed to the draft of the manuscript and revised the final version of the paper.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was supported through the Connect2restore project (TED2021-129589B-I00) funded by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Agencia Estatal de Investigación) and “Unión Europea NextGenerationEU/PRTR” and the NextDive Project (PID2021-124187NB-I00) funded by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Agencia Estatal de Investigación) and “FEDER Una manera de hacer Europa”.

A.Z-A. was financially supported by a Margarita Salas contract financed by the European Union (NextGenerationEU, Ministerio de Universidades y Plan de Recuperacion, Transformacion y Resiliencia) through the call of the Universidad de Oviedo (Asturias).

DATA AVAILABILITY

sabinaNSDM package and example data is available from the GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/geoSABINA/sabinaNSDM>

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Acevedo, P., Jiménez-Valverde, A., Lobo, J.M. & Real, R. (2012) Delimiting the geographical background in species distribution modelling. *Journal of Biogeography*, **39**, 1383-1390.
- Adde, A., Rey, P.-L., Brun, P., Külling, N., Fopp, F., Altermatt, F., Broennimann, O., Lehmann, A., Petitpierre, B., Zimmermann, N.E., Pellissier, L. & Guisan, A. (2023a) N-SDM: a high-performance computing pipeline for Nested Species Distribution Modelling. *Ecography*, **2023**, e06540.
- Adde, A., Rey, P.-L., Fopp, F., Petitpierre, B., Schweiger, A.K., Broennimann, O., Lehmann, A., Zimmermann, N.E., Altermatt, F., Pellissier, L. & Guisan, A. (2023b) Too many candidates: Embedded covariate selection procedure for species distribution modelling with the covsel R package. *Ecological Informatics*, 102080.
- Araújo, M.B., Anderson, R.P., Márcia Barbosa, A., Beale, C.M., Dormann, C.F., Early, R., Garcia, R.A., Guisan, A., Maiorano, L., Naimi, B., O'Hara, R.B., Zimmermann, N.E. & Rahbek, C. (2019) Standards for distribution models in biodiversity assessments. *Science Advances*, **5**, eaat4858.
- Araújo, M.B. & Guisan, A. (2006) Five (or so) challenges for species distribution modelling. *Journal of Biogeography*, **33**, 1676-1688.
- Araújo, M.B. & New, M. (2007) Ensemble forecasting of species distributions. *Trends in ecology and evolution*, **22**, 42-47.
- Booth, T.H., Nix, H.A., Busby, J.R. & Hutchinson, M.F. (2014) bioclim: the first species distribution modelling package, its early applications and relevance to most current MaxEnt studies. *Diversity and distributions*, **20**, 1-9.
- Carrillo-García, C., Girola-Iglesias, L., Guijarro, M., Hernando, C., Madrigal, J. & Mateo, R.G. (2023) Ecological niche models applied to post-megafire vegetation restoration in the context of climate change. *Science of The Total Environment*, **855**, 158858.
- Chevalier, M., Broennimann, O., Cornuault, J. & Guisan, A. (2021) Data integration methods to account for spatial niche truncation effects in regional projections of species distribution. *Ecological Applications*, **31**, e02427.
- Chevalier, M., Zarzo-Arias, A., Guélat, J., Mateo, R.G. & Guisan, A. (2022) Accounting for niche truncation to improve spatial and temporal predictions of species distributions. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, **10**.
- Di Cola, V., Broennimann, O., Petitpierre, B., Randin, C., Engler, R., Dubuis, A., D'Amen, M., Pellissier, L., Pottier, J., Pio, D., Salamin, N., Breiner, F.T., Mateo, R.G., Hordijk, W. & Guisan, A. (2017) **Ecospat: an R package for the support of spatial analyses and modelling of species niches and distributions**. *Ecography*, **40**, 764–787.
- Elith, J., Graham, C.H., Anderson, R.P., Dudík, M., Ferrier, S., Guisan, A., Hijmans, R.J., Huettmann, F., Leathwick, J.R., Lehmann, A., Li, J., Lohmann, L.G., Loiselle, B.A., Manion, G., Moritz, C., Nakamura, M., Nakazawa, Y., Overton, J.M., Peterson, A.T., Phillips, S.J., Richardson, K., Scachetti-Pereira, R., Schapire, R.E., Soberón, J., Williams, S., Wisz, M.S. & Zimmermann, N.E. (2006) Novel methods improve prediction of species' distributions from occurrence data. *Ecography*, **29**, 129-151.

- Gallien, L., Douzet, R., Pratte, S., Zimmermann, N.E. & Thuiller, W. (2012) Invasive species distribution models – how violating the equilibrium assumption can create new insights. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, **21**, 1126-1136.
- Goicolea, T., Adde, A., Broennimann, O., García-Viñas, J.I., Gastón, A., Aroca-Fernández, M.J., Guisan, A. & Mateo, R.G. (In Press) Hierarchical Species Distribution Models to Overcome Niche Truncation in National-Scale Studies. *Ecography*.
- Goodbody, T.R.H., Coops, N.C., Queinnec, M., White, J.C., Tompalski, P., Hudak, A.T., Auty, D., Valbuena, R., LeBoeuf, A., Sinclair, I., McCartney, G., Prieur, J.-F. & Woods, M.E. (2023) sgsR: a structurally guided sampling toolbox for LiDAR-based forest inventories. *Forestry: An International Journal of Forest Research*, **96**, 411-424.
- Guisan, A., Chevalier, M., Adde, A., Zarzo-Arias, A., Goicolea, T., Broennimann, O., Petitpierre, B., Scherrer, D., Rey, P.-L., Collart, F., Riva, F., Steen, B. & Mateo, R.G. (Under review) Spatially-nested hierarchical species distribution models to avoid niche truncation. *Journal of Ecology*.
- Guisan, A., Thuiller, W. & Zimmermann, N.E. (2017) *Habitat Suitability and Distribution Models. With Applications in R*. Cambridge University Press.
- Guisan, A., Tingley, R., Baumgartner, J.B., Naujokaitis-Lewis, I., Sutcliffe, P.R., Tulloch, A.I.T., Regan, T.J., Brotons, L., McDonald-Madden, E., Mantyka-Pringle, C., Martin, T.G., Rhodes, J.R., Maggini, R., Setterfield, S.A., Elith, J., Schwartz, M.W., Wintle, B.A., Broennimann, O., Austin, M., Ferrier, S., Kearney, M.R., Possingham, H.P. & Buckley, Y.M. (2013) Predicting species distributions for conservation decisions. *Ecology Letters*, **16**, 1424-1435.
- Guisan, A. & Zimmermann, N.E. (2000) Predictive habitat distribution models in ecology. *Ecological Modelling*, **135**, 147-186.
- Marmion, M., Parviainen, M., Luoto, M., Heikkinen, R.K. & Thuiller, W. (2009) Evaluation of consensus methods in predictive species distribution modelling. *Diversity and distributions*, **15**, 59-69.
- Mateo, R.G., Aroca-Fernández, M.J., Gastón, A., Gómez-Rubio, V., Saura, S. & García-Viñas, J.I. (2019a) Looking for an optimal hierarchical approach for ecologically meaningful niche modelling. *Ecological Modelling*, **409**, 108735.
- Mateo, R.G., Broennimann, O., Petitpierre, B., Muñoz, J., van Rooy, J., Laenen, B., Guisan, A. & Vanderpoorten, A. (2015) What is the potential of spread in invasive bryophytes? *Ecography*, **38**, 480-487.
- Mateo, R.G., Croat, T.B., Felicísimo, Á.M. & Muñoz, J. (2010) Profile or group discriminative techniques? Generating reliable species distribution models using pseudo-absences and target-group absences from natural history collections. *Diversity and distributions*, **16**, 84-94.
- Mateo, R.G., Gastón, A., Aroca-Fernández, M.J., Broennimann, O., Guisan, A., Saura, S. & García-Viñas, J.I. (2019b) Hierarchical species distribution models in support of vegetation conservation at the landscape scale. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, **30**, 386-396.
- Mateo, R.G., Mokany, K. & Guisan, A. (2017) Biodiversity Models: What If Unsaturation Is the Rule? *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, **32**, 556-566.
- McGill, B.J. (2010) Matters of Scale. *Science*, **328**, 575-576.
- Moudry, V., Bazzichetto, M., Remelgado, R., Devillers, R., Lenoir, J., Mateo, R.G., Lembrechts, J., Sillero, N., Lecours, V., Cord, A., Bartak, V., Balej, P., Rocchini, D.,

- Torresani, M., Arenas-Castro, S., Man, M., Prajzlerova, D., Gdulova, K., Prosek, J., Marchetto, E., Zarzo-Arias, A., Gabor, L., Leroy, F., Martini, M., Malavasi, M., Gatti, R., Wild, J. & Šímová, P. (Under Review) Optimising Species Distribution Models: Sample size, positional error, and sampling bias matter. *Ecography*.
- Petitpierre, B., McDougall, K., Seipel, T., Broennimann, O., Guisan, A. & Kueffer, C. (2016) Will climate change increase the risk of plant invasions into mountains? *Ecological Applications*, **26**, 530-544.
- Scherrer, D., Esperon-Rodriguez, M., Beaumont, L.J., Barradas, V.L. & Guisan, A. (2021) National assessments of species vulnerability to climate change strongly depend on selected data sources. *Diversity and distributions*, **27**, 1367-1382.
- Sillero, N., Arenas-Castro, S., Enriquez-Urzelai, U., Vale, C.G., Sousa-Guedes, D., Martínez-Freiría, F., Real, R. & Barbosa, A.M. (2021) Want to model a species niche? A step-by-step guideline on correlative ecological niche modelling. *Ecological Modelling*, **456**, 109671.
- Sillero, N., Campos, J.C., Arenas-Castro, S. & Barbosa, A.M. (2023) A curated list of R packages for ecological niche modelling. *Ecological Modelling*, **476**, 110242.
- Thuiller, W., Brotons, L., Araújo, M.B. & Lavorel, S. (2004) Effects of restricting environmental range of data to project current and future species distributions. *Ecography*, **27**, 165-172.
- Thuiller, W., Lafourcade, B., Engler, R. & Araújo, M.B. (2009) BIOMOD - a platform for ensemble forecasting of species distributions. *Ecography*, **32**, 369-373.
- Vaughan, D. & Dancho, M. (2022) furr: Apply Mapping Functions in Parallel using Futures. <https://github.com/DavisVaughan/furr>.
- Zurell, D., Franklin, J., König, C., Bouchet, P.J., Dormann, C.F., Elith, J., Fandos, G., Feng, X., Guillera-Aroita, G., Guisan, A., Lahoz-Monfort, J.J., Leitão, P.J., Park, D.S., Peterson, A.T., Rapacciuolo, G., Schmatz, D.R., Schröder, B., Serra-Diaz, J.M., Thuiller, W., Yates, K.L., Zimmermann, N.E. & Merow, C. (2020) A standard protocol for reporting species distribution models. *Ecography*, **43**, 1261-1276.